

Synthesis of Coumarins from Phenols and β -Ketonic Esters. Part V. Constitution of Chlororesorcin and Chlororesorcylaldehyde.

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Reinhard (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1878, *ii*, 17, 336) prepared a chlororesorcin by the action of sulphuryl chloride on a dry ethereal solution of resorcin. It is not possible to determine the position of the Cl atom by preparing the chlororesorcin from the two nitroresorcins (*e.g.* 2- and 4-nitroresorcin) as the action of sodium nitrite on a cooled solution of 2-aminoresorcin hydrochloride leads to the formation of a nitroso derivative (Kauffmann and Pay, *Ber.*, 1906, 39, 323) and as diazotised 4-aminoresorcin, when submitted to Sandmayer's reaction, gives resorcinol-azochlororesorcinol (Voroschov and Gorkov, *J. Gen. Chem. Russ.*, 1932, 2, 421). Clark (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 55, 319) has recently proved the structure of chlororesorcin to be 4-chlororesorcin by nitrating chlorobenzene and replacing the nitro groups by OH groups *via* the diazo-reaction.

The condensation of halogenated and negatively substituted phenols with β -ketonic esters forming substituted coumarins has also furnished a ready means for determining the constitution of substituted phenols and their derivatives.

Chlororesorcin condenses with acetoacetic ester and its *C*-methyl derivative to form 6-chloro- or 8-chlorocoumarins (Chakravarti and Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 622). The nitration of β methylumbelliferone (*cf.* Pechmann and Cohen, *Ber.*, 1901, 34, 666) and of 3:4-dimethylumbelliferone gives 8-nitro derivatives as they are identical with the condensation products of 2-nitroresorcin with acetoacetic ester and its *C*-methyl derivative (Chakravarti and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*). Pechmann and Cohen (*loc. cit.*) record the m.p. of the acetyl derivative of nitro- β -methylumbelliferone as 165°. This seems to be inaccurate as the acetyl derivative melted at 198°, and on deacetylation with 20% sulphuric acid it gave the original nitroumbelliferone melting at 256°. 8-Nitroumbelliferones on reduction with stannous chloride and hydrochloric acid gave 8-amino-umbelliferones which formed stable diazoanhydrides (I). The

diazoanhydrides on treatment with cuprous chloride in hydrochloric acid gave 8-chloroumbelliferones which are different from the condensation products of chlororesorcin with acetoacetic esters.

The condensation products of chlororesorcin with acetoacetic esters are, therefore, not 8-chloroumbelliferones but 6-chloroumbelliferones. Chlororesorcin is, therefore, 4-chlororesorcin, as has been shown by Clark (*loc. cit.*). It is rather strange that Lichoscherstov and Tzimbalist (*J. Gen. Chem. Russ.*, 1933, 3, 162) describe the chlororesorcin (b. p. 259·5°, m. p. 102·5°) obtained by the chlorination of resorcin in presence of dichlorocarbamide as 4-chlororesorcin and identical with Reinhard's product, though Reinhard's product melts at 89° and boils at 259° (Reinhard, *loc. cit.*; Clark, *loc. cit.*).

The singular behaviour of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin and 7-hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin in forming 8-nitro derivatives in preference to 6-nitro derivatives is noteworthy. Coumarin itself, however, on nitration gives a mixture of 8-nitro- and 6-nitro derivatives, the latter being largely in excess (*cf.* Dey, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, 4, 198). 7-Hydroxycoumarin (umbelliferone), however, on nitration, has been found to give a mixture of 8-nitro- and 6-nitro derivatives. The two products have been separated by crystallisation from glacial acetic acid, one melting at 245° and the other at 220°. Clayton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1400) described the nitration of umbelliferone and isolated a product (m. p. 245°) which was shown by analogy with the nitro derivative of 4-methylumbelliferone (Pechmann and Cohen, *loc. cit.*) to be 8-nitroumbelliferone.

The product melting at 245° has now been proved to be 8 nitroumbelliferone in the following way: On reduction it gave amino-umbelliferone, which formed a soluble diazoanhydride and finally gave a chlorocoumarin (m. p. 263°) by treatment with cuprous chloride and hydrochloric acid, which was different from 6-chloroumbelliferone (m. p. 271°) obtained by malic acid condensation from 4-chlororesorcin. Hence the chloroumbelliferone obtained from nitroumbelliferone is

8-chloroumbelliferone and the nitroumbelliferone is 8-nitro derivative. A direct method of synthesising 8-nitroumbelliferone by the condensation of 2-nitroresorcin with malic acid resulted in failure as 2-nitroresorcin was very easily sulphonated. Hence in the nitroumbelliferone, described by Clayton, the nitro group is in position 8, though Weiss and Kratz (*Monatsch.*, 1929, **51**, 386) are doubtful about the position of the nitro group, as it is not identical with the nitroumbelliferone (m. p. 228°) prepared by them by the action of ethyl ethoxymethylene mglonate on 2-nitroresorcin in presence of alcoholic sodium ethoxide.

The formation of a coumarin from chlororesorcyaldehyde (Gattermann. *Annalen*, 1907, **357**, 313) by its condensation with malonic acid has settled the position of substituents in chlororesorcyaldehyde. Chlororesorcyaldehyde, prepared in the present investigation by Roger Adam's modification of Gattermann's reaction, does not condense with malonic acid and attempts to condense the dicarbomethoxychlororesorcyaldehyde with malonic acid in pyridine solution in presence of piperidine also failed. The dicarbomethoxy derivative, however, condensed with malonic acid in glacial acetic acid solution (*cf.* Späth, *Monatsch.*, 1920, **41**, 271 ; Mitter and Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 262) yielding a mixture of 2:4-dicarbomethoxycinnamic acid (traces only) and carbomethoxychloroumbelliferone carboxylic acid. The latter, when boiled with sodium carbonate solution, gave chloroumbelliferone carboxylic acid (m. p. 284°), which on heating yielded chloroumbelliferone (m. p. 271°) identical with the condensation product of chlororesorcin and malic acid, *i.e.*, 6-chloro-7-hydroxycoumarin. Hence, chlororesorcyaldehyde is 5-chlororesorcyaldehyde, the reaction taking place as follows :

EXPERIMENTAL.

8-Chloro-4-methylumbelliferone.—The diazoanhydride of 8-amino-4-methylumbelliferone (5 g., Pechmann and Cohen, *loc. cit.*) was

dissolved in the least quantity of concentrated hydrochloric acid and the solution added in the cold to cuprous chloride solution (prepared by adding 100 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid to 10 g. of copper carbonate and heating with copper turnings till colourless). The reddish precipitate obtained was washed with concentrated hydrochloric acid and then with water. It was finally crystallised from glacial acetic acid as light yellow prisms, m. p. 267°. (Found: Cl, 16.24. $C_{10}H_7O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 16.8 per cent).

The *acetyl* derivative, prepared by heating the substance with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate, crystallised from alcohol as colourless prisms, m. p. 188.89°. (Found: Cl, 13.9. $C_{12}H_9O_4Cl$ requires Cl, 14.05 per cent). The condensation product of chlororesorcin and acetoacetic ester, however, melts at 280° (acetyl derivative, m. p. 168°, cf. Chakravarti and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

8-Nitro-3:4-dimethylumbelliferone.—To a solution of dimethylumbelliferone (20 g., condensation product of resorcin with methyl acetoacetic ester) in concentrated sulphuric acid (100 c.c.), cooled in a freezing mixture, a mixture of nitric acid (*d* 1.52, 6 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (12 c.c.) was added drop by drop and the solution mechanically stirred. Stirring was continued for 1 hour more. The mixture was poured into ice-water and the yellow precipitate was filtered and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as yellow prisms, m. p. 260°, yield 14 g. It was proved to be identical with the product obtained by the condensation of 2-nitroresorcin and methylacetoacetic ester by mixed m. p. and also by the identity of their acetyl derivatives (m. p. 198°, Chakravarti and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

8-Amino-3:4-dimethylumbelliferone.—8-Nitro-3:4-dimethylumbelliferone (11 g.) was mixed with stannous chloride (35 g.), concentrated hydrochloric acid (30 c.c.) and rectified spirit (30 c.c.). The mixture was heated on a wire-gauge till a clear solution was obtained, when more concentrated hydrochloric acid (60 c.c.) was added and the solution allowed to cool, crystals of double salt separated after 1 hour. These were filtered and dissolved in the least quantity of water and tin was removed completely by means of sulphuretted hydrogen. The filtered solution was then heated and sodium acetate added when the amino-umbelliferone separated, which was collected and crystallised from dilute alcohol as light greenish-yellow needles, m. p. 272°, yield 5 g. (Found: N, 6.7. $C_{11}H_{11}O_3N$ requires N, 6.8 per cent).

The *diazoanhydride* was obtained by adding in the cold a solution of sodium nitrite (1.2 g.) to a solution of 8-amino-7-hydroxy-3:4-dimethylcoumarin (3.5 g.) in hydrochloric acid (10 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid and 150 c.c. of water). A reddish yellow precipitate was obtained, which was collected and crystallised from hot water in red shining needles, m.p. 172°, yield 3 g. (Found: N, 12.9. $C_{11}H_8O_3N_2$ requires N, 12.96 per cent).

8 *Chloro-3:4-dimethylumbelliferone*.—The diazoanhydride was dissolved in the least quantity of concentrated hydrochloric acid and the solution added to cooled cuprous chloride solution prepared as before. The solution was stirred, when nitrogen was given off and a red precipitate separated. It was washed with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid as small colourless prisms, m.p. 272°, the m.p. being considerably depressed when mixed with the condensation product of chlororesorcin with methyl acetoacetic ester (m.p. 248°, Chakravarti and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*) (Found: Cl, 15.51. $C_{11}H_9O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 15.8 per cent).

8-*Nitroumbelliferone* and 6-*nitroumbelliferone*.—To the cooled solution of umbelliferone (25 g.) in concentrated sulphuric acid (140 c.c.), which was mechanically stirred, a mixture of nitric acid (d 1.52, 6 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (15 c.c.) was gradually added drop by drop and the solution stirred for 1 hour more. The solution was poured into ice and the reddish yellow precipitate was collected and crystallised from glacial acetic acid. By repeated crystallisations from glacial acetic acid two products were obtained: one melting at 245°, yield 8 g. and the other m.p. 220, yield 1 g. The product melting at 245° is 8-nitro-7-hydroxycoumarin and is identical with Clayton's compound (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, 97, 1400). (Found: N, 7.0. Calc. for $C_9H_5O_5N$: N, 6.76 per cent). The *acetyl* derivative, prepared in the usual manner, crystallised from glacial acetic acid, m.p. 185°. The second product melting at 220° is 6-nitro-7-hydroxycoumarin. (Found: N, 6.91. $C_9H_5O_5N$ requires N, 6.76 per cent). The *acetyl* derivative, prepared as usual, crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 180°, the m.p. being considerably depressed when mixed with the acetyl derivative of 8-nitro-7-hydroxycoumarin.

8 *Amino-7-hydroxycoumarin* was obtained from 8-nitro-7-hydroxycoumarin (7.3 g.) by heating with stannous chloride (24 g.) concentrated hydrochloric acid (20 c.c.) and rectified spirit (20 c.c.). 40 C.c. of hydrochloric acid were then added and the solution allowed to cool when colourless crystals of double salt separated. These were

filtered, dissolved in a small quantity of water and the tin removed by sulphuretted hydrogen. The filtrate was gently warmed and sodium acetate added till precipitation was complete. A greenish substance was obtained, which crystallised from alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. 248-50°. (Found: N, 7.94. $C_9H_7O_3N$ requires N, 7.9 per cent).

8-Chloro-7-hydroxycoumarin.—8-Amino-7-hydroxycoumarin was diazotised in the usual way and the diazo solution treated with cold cuprous chloride solution, when nitrogen was evolved and a red precipitate separated. It was collected, washed with concentrated hydrochloric acid and then with water and crystallised from glacial acetic acid in light yellow needles, m.p. 263°. (Found: Cl, 18.3. $C_9H_5O_3Cl$ requires Cl, 18.06 per cent). The condensation product of chlororesorcin and malic acid melts at 271° (Chakravarti and Ghosh, *loc. cit.*).

Preparation of chlororesorcylaldehyde.—Dry hydrochloric acid gas was bubbled for 2 hours through a solution of chlororesorcin (25 g.) in dry ether (200 c.c.) containing anhydrous zinc cyanide (40 g.), the solution being cooled in a freezing mixture and stirred with a mercury-seal stirrer. The ether was decanted and the solid mass was refluxed with water on a water-bath. On cooling a red solid separated from which chlororesorcylaldehyde was obtained by repeated crystallisation from water as light yellow needles, m.p. 100°, yield 12 g.

Preparation of 6-chloroumbelliferone from chlororesorcylaldehyde.—Dicarbomethoxychlororesorcylaldehyde, m. p. 58°, was obtained in quantitative yield by treating a solution of chlororesorcylaldehyde in *N*-NaOH with methyl chlorocarbonate in the cold. The crude dicarbomethoxy derivative (2 g.) and malonic acid (2 g.) were dissolved in glacial acetic acid (2 c. c.) and heated on a boiling water-bath for 10 hours. The cold solution was diluted with water and the precipitate consisting of dicarbomethoxycinnamic acid and carbomethoxyumbelliferone carboxylic acid was treated with 10% potassium bicarbonate solution under ice-cooling, when the cinnamic acid passed into solution and the coumarin remained insoluble (*cf.* Mitter and Saha, *loc. cit.*). The insoluble carbomethoxychloroumbelliferone carboxylic acid was boiled with an excess of 10% sodium carbonate solution for 10 minutes. A highly fluorescent solution was obtained which on acidification with hydrochloric acid (1:1) gave a precipitate of umbelliferone carboxylic acid, which crystallised from alcohol,

m. p. 284°. When heated to about 260°-270° in a metal bath chloroumbelliferone began to sublime as colourless prisms, m. p. 271° (mixed m. p. with 6-chloroumbelliferone, the condensation product of 4-chlororesorcin with malic acid is also 271°).

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A Semi-micro Method of Determining Total Nitrogen of Air-dry Soils.

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The present investigation was undertaken with a view to find out if Pregl's Micro-Kjeldahl method (Fritz Pregl, "Die Quantitative Organische Micro Analyse," 1930, p. 120) could be applied in the determination of the total nitrogen of soils and thus to save time and reagents otherwise necessary for the macro method. In the micro method, it is impossible to work with 3-5 mg. (of the soil) which is the amount usually employed in micro analyses of pure organic compounds due to the almost negligible amount of ammonia that would be obtained. Hence 0.5 g. of the soil was found to be the suitable quantity. Elimination of sampling error, however, is to be carefully guarded against. An experiment was carried out with stock soil to test the method.

EXPERIMENTAL.

About 1 lb of soil was sieved through a 1 mm. sieve and a sub-sample containing about 50 g. was made in the usual way. The sub-sample was thoroughly ground in an agate mortar and sieved through a 30 mesh sieve, the process of grinding being repeated until all the soils passed through the sieve. Now the finely ground soil was spread over a glazed paper in thin layer and mixed thoroughly. With the help of a fine nickel spatula, about 0.5 g. of soil taken from different places was weighed in micro weighing bottles, and taken in a micro Kjeldahl digestion flask and about 0.5 g. of sodium sulphate